

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CREATIVE RESEARCH THOUGHTS | ISSN: 2320 - 2882

An International Open Access, Peer-reviewed, Refereed Journal

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“Effectiveness of a Structured Teaching Programme on Knowledge and Practice Regarding Prevention of Protein Energy Malnutrition Among Mothers of Under-Five Children: A Pre-Experimental Study in Selected Block-Level Communities of Madhya Pradesh, India.”

Published In IJCRT (www.ijert.org) & 7.97 Impact Factor by Google Scholar

Volume 14 Issue 6 July 2026 , Date of Publication: 03-July-2026

UGC Approved Journal No: 49023 (18)

PAPER ID : IJCRT2603660

Registration ID : 315264

Scholarly open access journals, Peer-reviewed, and Refereed Journals, Impact factor 7.97 (Calculate by google scholar and Semantic Scholar | AI-Powered Research Tool) , Multidisciplinary, Monthly Journal

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Website: www.ijcrt.org | Email id: editor@ijcrt.org | ESTD: 2013